

Studies on the Decomposition and Reactions of Urea.
Part IV. On the Mechanism of the Formation
of Ammelide, etc.

BY (LATE) JNANENDRA MOHON DAS-GUPTA.

Investigations on the mechanism of the formation of ammelide by the decomposition of urea by heat, have been found of interest from several points of view. Apart from the complex nature of this mechanism, which is by no means clear, closely related to this problem are probably (i) the origin of cyanuric acid from the decomposition of urea by heat, (ii) the mechanism of the reaction of biuret. Solution of the first problem might, therefore, throw light on the others and *vice versa*. The possibility of cyanuric acid being the precursor of ammelide which would be formed by the direct interaction of the former with ammonia is disposed of by the observation that ammelide is not obtained by heating cyanuric acid with urea below 180° , though under such condition urea is an excellent source of ammonia (Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 111, 117). The alternative explanation due to Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 2275), appears defective when certain facts are taken into consideration. His results would show that ammelide is formed below 180° . But with a more careful regulation of the temperature it is found that ammelide is not formed appreciably below 190° , under various conditions; while it is produced to an appreciable extent only at about 195° , which is the decomposition point of biuret. This would suggest that the formation of ammelide is probably preceded by the decomposition of biuret, its formation being then directly connected with the latter but not in the way shown by Werner.

The experiments described clearly establish the following facts:

(i) Though biuret is considerably formed between $150-180^{\circ}$, yet no ammelide is produced, although urea under such condition is an excellent source of cyanic acid (*loc. cit.*).

(ii) Taking into consideration that the ammonia evolved may interfere with the action of cyanic acid on biuret, the decompositions have been studied in an atmosphere of hydrochloric acid gas. Even under such condition no ammelide is formed below 185° .

It is quite natural to expect the formation of dicyanic acid as a result of the decomposition of biuret when it is remembered that most substituted ureas decompose in the two directions shown above. It has been found that dicyanic acid is formed from the decomposition of nitrobiuret (Davis and Blanchard, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1801). A further evidence of such decomposition is afforded by the formation of phenylbiuret from the action of biuret on aniline. The latter reaction would appear to take place thus:

Since, however, its formation is always accompanied by the simultaneous production of diphenylurea, the above simple mechanism is not sufficient. Evidently in the above reaction biuret undergoes decomposition first as in (I) and then reacts thus:

Dicyanic acid.

It may be observed from the experiments described below, that though biuret decomposes at about 195° in the solid state, the decomposition point is much lowered in presence of aniline (150-80°). (*cf.* decomposition of urea in various solvents).

The formation of ammelide in the reaction of phosgene with ammonia (Hantzsch and Stuer, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 1022; Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 113, 694) is not different to account for according to this view:

EXPERIMENTAL.

Decomposition of urea by heat.—Urea (5 g.) was heated in a weighed hard glass test tube (12 × 2 cm.) in an oil-bath to the desired temperature. It was then maintained at the temperature for 15 minutes

or more, as required, then cooled, weighed and from the difference the loss due to the escape of gases found out. The residue was dissolved in water (40-50 c.c.). Biuret was estimated colorimetrically by comparing with a standard solution (0.1%) and cyanuric acid by titration with *N*/10-alkali (phenolphthalein as indicator), after removing any ammonia present in the solution by blowing air through it (15 to 20 min.). In case there is a mixture of ammelide and cyanuric acid, these can be satisfactorily estimated by the following modification. An excess of measured volume of *N*-alkali was added to the mixture (obtained by adding 50 c.c. of water to the fused mass), so that a clear solution was obtained. An equal volume of a *N*-acid was then added, which threw down the ammelide, while the cyanuric acid remained completely dissolved. The precipitate is washed several times with cold water and the washings added to the filtrate. It is next dried and weighed. Cyanuric acid is estimated by titrating the filtrate with *N*/10-alkali and urea by adding nitric acid to a concentrated fraction of the same or from difference. In the experiments noted in Table III, urea (15 g.) was melted in a 100 c.c. conical flask and a slow current of dry HCl gas was directed on to the surface of the liquid (3-4 bubbles per minute).

TABLE I.

Action of heat on urea at different temperatures.

	170° for 15 mins.	180° for 15 mins.	180-85° for 15 mins.	190-95° for 15 mins.	150-160° for ½ hr. and then at 200-10° for ½ hr
Biuret	24.2%	28.3%	30.4%	23.3%	4.5%
Cyanuric	Trace	0.4	0.8	5.4	26.3
Ammelide	Nil	Nil	Nil	2.5	10.8
Urea	71.2	64.3	61.0	52.4	33.7
Loss (NH ₃ + NHCO)	4.2	7.1	8.3	16.4	24.7

TABLE II.

Action of heat on urea for different periods.

Temperature = 170°.

	30 min.	45 min.	60 min.	75 min.	90 min.
Loss (NH ₃ + NHCO)	2.1%	2.5%	3.4%	3.8%	5.2%
Sublimate (NH ₄ OCN)	2.8	4.2	5.0	6.1	7.3
Biuret	30.5	28.2	25.0	22.5	20.5
Cyanuric acid	0.1	0.12	0.14	0.18	0.2
Ammelide	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil

TABLE III.

Action of heat on urea in an atmosphere of HCl.

	175° for 15 mins.	180° for 15 mins.	180-85° for 45 min.
Biuret	22.5%	21.9%	18.5%
Ammelide	Nil	Nil	Trace
Urea	63.0	60.1	55.2

Action of biuret on aniline.—Anhydrous biuret (3.4 g.) and aniline (3.1 g.) were heated together in an oil-bath to the desired temperature. The melt was extracted with warm water (30-40 c.c.) and filtered hot. The precipitate on crystallisation from alcohol yields diphenylurea, m.p. and mixed m.p. 235°. The filtrate, freed from aniline, was charcoaled, concentrated, cooled and treated with ether. From the ethereal solution, phenylbiuret crystallised out and was recrystallised from hot water, m. p. and mixed m.p. 165°. The aqueous solution on concentration to a small volume yields a small quantity of phenylurea, m.p. 145°.

	160° for ½ hr.	170° for ½ hr.	183-85° for ½ hr.
Biuret decomposed	78.5%	84.7%	88.0%
Phenylbiuret	11.1	10.3	9.5
Diphenylurea	36.5	40.1	45.1

The results are expressed in proportion to the respective theoretical yields.

